

Overview of the distribution and biogeography of the Heteroptera (Hemiptera) Collection in The Biodiversity Science Museum of Atatürk University, Erzurum-Türkiye (ABBM)

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ABSTRACT: This study reviewed faunistic and systematic studies on the Heteroptera fauna collected from numerous localities in Anatolia, particularly Eastern Anatolia between 1963 and 2017 and their distribution and biogeography are analyzed material in Atatürk University Biodiversity Science Museum, Erzurum, Türkiye (ABBM). Totally, 407 species in 221 genera belonging to the following 30 families are recorded. It was determined that 357 species were from Eastern Anatolia, 105 species from South-eastern Anatolia, 156 species from Black Sea, 171 species from Central Anatolia, 201 species from Mediterranean, 121 species from Aegean and 146 species from Marmara. Species composition, diversity and proportion of endemism varies considerably among the geographic regions of the country.

KEYWORDS: Heteroptera, Distribution, Biogeography, Atatürk University Biodiversity Science Museum (ABBM), Erzurum, Türkiye

INTRODUCTION

Insects are the most diverse group, accounting for more than half of the world's identified organisms. The order Hemiptera is the fifth largest order among the insect orders (Cassis et al., 2006; Zhang, 2011). The Heteroptera known as true bugs, is a suborder of the

Hemiptera and represent the largest and most diverse group of hemimetabolous insects. This diverse group exhibiting both phytophagous and zoophagous feeding habits affects nearly every aspect of our environment (Schuh & Slater, 1995). Their roles as plant feeders, hemolymph-sucking parasites, invertebrate predators, or water-quality indicators

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make them unquestionably important organisms in our environment (Cassis et al., 2006; Henry, 2017). Worldwide are more than 45.254 species and 6184 genera. The numbers in the Palearctic regions are 9.365 species and 1632 genera (Aukema et al., 2013; Henry, 2017).

Türkiye occupies Asia Minor between the Mediterranean Sea and the Black Sea and stretches into continental Europe. It is a mountainous country averaging about 1000 meters in altitude. The topographic and climatic diversity of the region are important preconditions for the development of a rich and diverse fauna. Türkiye is generally divided into

seven biogeographical regions. These are the Marmara Region, the Aegean Region, the Mediterranean Region, the Black Sea Region, and the Central, Eastern and South Eastern Anatolian Regions (Fig.1) (Yıldırım 2012a, b; Yazıcı et al., 2019). It has been known to possess a rich fauna of Heteroptera. Thus, some faunistic and systematic studies about the Heteroptera have been conducted by both foreign and native researchers in Türkiye. However, no attempt has been undertaken to evaluate the distribution and biogeography of Heteroptera in Türkiye. Yet, such a study is essential for researchers who are interested in Miridae in the West Palearctic region including Türkiye.

Figure 1. Biogeographical map of Türkiye (1/3.200.000) (Anonymous, 2024).

The knowledge of the Heteroptera fauna of Türkiye was first summarized by the works of Hoberlandt (1952, 1956). In the first study conducted in 1952 were reported 66 species and in the study in 1956 were reported 862 species. Later, Seidenstücker (1957, 1958, 1960), Wagner (1959, 1960, 1966), Linnavuori (1965), Tuatay et al. (1966, 1972), Önder (1976, 1980, 1982), Lodos & Önder (1978, 1979, 1980, 1982, 1983), Lodos et al. (1978, 1984, 1998, 1999, 2003), Önder et al. (1981, 1983, 1984, 1995a, 1995b, 2006), Pehlivan (1981), Çakır & Önder (1990), Çam (1993), Fent & Aktaç (1999, 2007, 2009), Tezcan & Önder (1999, 2003), Öz Saraç & Kıyak (2001), Kıyak et al. (2004), Özgen et al. (2005a,b), Dursun (2009, 2011a, b), Dursun & Fent (2009, 2011a,b, 2016, 2017), Abacıgil et al. (2010), Fent (2010, 2011), Kıyak & Akar (2010), Matocq & Özgen (2010), Yıldırım

et al. (2010, 2011, 2013a,b), Fent & Japoshvili (2012), Özgen (2012), Maral et al. (2013), Tezcan et al. (2013), Matocq et al. (2014), Yazıcı et al. (2014, 2015a,b), Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak (2015), Kıyak (2016), Yazıcı & Yıldırım (2016a,b,c), Çerçi & Koçak (2017), Yazıcı (2017), Aysal & Kıvan (2018), Çerçi et al. (2018), Fent & Dursun (2019, 2022), Özgen & Dioli (2019), Zengin & Dursun (2019), Çerçi & Tezcan (2020), Tezcan (2020), Akman & Dursun (2021), Çerçi & Özgen (2021), Kıyak & Baş (2021), Yılmaz & Dursun (2022), Çerçi et al. (2024) reported many species from Türkiye. In Türkiye more than 1500 species and 40 families of Heteroptera were recorded (Önder et al., 2006; Tezcan 2020, 2024). However, according to the latest research conducted by Çerçi et al. in 2024, 1668 species of Heteroptera have been recorded from Türkiye (664 species in the European part and

1633 species in the Anatolian part) until now.

Their findings emphasized that despite the abundant research devoted over the last 150 years to the Heteroptera fauna of Türkiye, it remains incomplete in the majority, if not in all, of the regions.

In addition, it strongly encourages further research, particularly in regions with small numbers of recorded species. This endeavor will undoubtedly lead to numerous novel discoveries and provide a better understanding of the true Heteroptera diversity in Türkiye. In that case, there is much challenging work to be done to understand better this taxonomically complex and economically important group of fascinating insects.

The Entomology Museum, Erzurum, Türkiye (EMET), located in the Plant Protection Department of Atatürk University Faculty of Agriculture, has been an important resource for many academics who have been doing scientific studies and research for a long time. In this museum, which was established within Atatürk University in 1966 in order to reveal the insect diversity in our country, there are more than 200 thousand insect individuals collected from various regions of Türkiye and different countries, including more than 10 thousand identified species and more than 100 insect species that are new to world literature. This museum is among the international insect museums and was a unit where many scientists from home and abroad carried out their research and project work. However, the materials in this museum were transferred to Atatürk University Biodiversity Science Museum (ABBM), Erzurum, Türkiye, which was established within Atatürk University in 2020, and all materials are kept here. This museum, as the first nature museum in Türkiye, preserves biological riches collected from many regions of our country. In this study, all of the samples examined are preserved at Atatürk University Biodiversity Science Museum (ABBM).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

In this paper, the previous publications on the Heteroptera of Atatürk University Biodiversity Science Museum (ABBM) are reviewed and the distribution and biogeography of the Turkish fauna of Heteroptera have been analyzed.

In addition, the endemic species are also discussed. The names of the taxa to which the specimens in the museum collection belong were reviewed for homonyms, synonyms, or incorrect spellings, and if there were any problems, they were updated with valid names.

In updating the names, the Index to Organism Names (ION) based on the Thomson Reuters database was used (Anonymous, 2015a), the Planetary Biodiversity Inventory (PBI) supported by the National Science Foundation (NSF) (Anonymous, 2015b) and the Dutch Entomological Institute. Contains all information in the Catalog of Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region (Aukema, 2022) volumes I-VI (Aukema & Rieger, 1995, 1996, 1999, 2001, 2006; Aukema *et al.* 2013), published by the Society of Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region (1995-2013) database was used.

All examined samples are preserved at Atatürk University Biodiversity Science Museum (ABBM), Erzurum, Türkiye. The classification of identified all specimens in this collection into taxa is given and listed in the table below (Table 1).

RESULTS

As a result, 4 species in 2 genera of Gerromorpha, 10 species in 5 genera of Nepomorpha, 3 species in one genus of Leptopodomorpha, 177 species in 93 genera of Cimicomorpha and 213 species in 120 genera of Pentatomomorpha are recorded. In total, 407 species belonging to 221 genera of 30 families of Heteroptera are recorded from Atatürk University Biodiversity Science Museum (ABBM) (Table 1).

Table 1: Distribution of Heteroptera in geographic regions of Türkiye.

Names of taxa	EA	SA	BS	CA	MD	A	M
Infraorder Gerromorpha							
Family Gerridae Leach, 1815							
Genus <i>Aquarius</i> Schellenberg, 1800							
<i>Aquarius paludum</i> (Fabricius, 1794)				+	+		
<i>Aquarius ventralis</i> (Fieber, 1860)	+		+		+		
Genus <i>Gerris</i> Fabricius, 1794							
<i>Gerris (Gerris) argentatus</i> Schummel, 1832	+					+	
<i>Gerris (Gerriselloides) lateralis</i> Schummel, 1832	+		+	+	+	+	
Infraorder Nepomorpha							
Family Belostomatidae Leach, 1815							
Genus <i>Lethocerus</i> Mayr, 1853							
<i>Lethocerus (Lethocerus) patruelis</i> (Stål, 1854)					+		+
Family Corixidae Leach, 1815							
Genus <i>Corixa</i> Geoffroy, 1762							
<i>Corixa affinis</i> Leach, 1817				+			
<i>Corixa panzeri</i> Fieber, 1848	+						
<i>Corixa punctata</i> (Illiger, 1807)				+			
Genus <i>Sigara</i> Fabricius, 1775							
<i>Sigara (Pseudovermicorixa) nigrolineata</i> (Fieber, 1848)	+						
<i>Sigara (Vermicorixa) lateralis</i> (Leach, 1817)	+						
Family Nepidae Latreille, 1802							
Genus <i>Nepa</i> Linnaeus, 1758							
<i>Nepa cinerea</i> Linnaeus, 1758				+			
Family Notonectidae Latreille, 1802							
Genus <i>Notonecta</i> Linnaeus, 1758							
<i>Notonecta maculata</i> Fabricius, 1794		+			+		
<i>Notonecta glauca</i> Linnaeus, 1758		+		+			
<i>Notonecta meridionalis</i> Poisson, 1926	+			+			
Infraorder Leptopodomorpha							
Family Saldidae Amyot & Serville, 1843							
Genus <i>Saldula</i> Van Duzee, 1914							
<i>Saldula amplicollis</i> (Reuter, 1891)	+						

<i>Saldula arenicola</i> (Scholtz, 1847)	+						
<i>Saldula pallipes</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	+						
Infraorder Cimicomorpha							
Family Anthocoridae Fieber, 1836							
Genus Anthocoris Fallén, 1814							
<i>Anthocoris nemoralis</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	+				+		
<i>Anthocoris nemorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	+				+		
<i>Anthocoris pilosus</i> (Jakovlev, 1877)	+		+	+	+		
Genus Orius Wolff, 1811							
<i>Orius (Heterorius) minutus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+	+	+		+		
<i>Orius (Orius) niger</i> (Wolff, 1811)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus Temnostethus Fieber, 1860							
<i>Temnostethus (Ectemnus) reduvinus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)	+		+		+		
<i>Temnostethus (Montandoniella) dacicus</i> (Puton, 1888)	+				+		
Genus Xylocoris Dufour, 1831							
<i>Xylocoris (Xylocoris) ciliatus</i> (Jakovlev, 1877)	+				+		
Family Lyctocoridae Reuter, 1884							
Genus Lyctocoris Hahn, 1836							
<i>Lyctocoris dimidiatus</i> (Spinola, 1837)	+						
Family Miridae Hahn, 1831							
Genus Acetropis Fieber, 1858							
<i>Acetropis carinata</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1841)	+			+	+	+	
Genus Adelphocoris Reuter, 1896							
<i>Adelphocoris lineolatus</i> (Goeze, 1778)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Adelphocoris seticornis</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	+		+				+
<i>Adelphocoris vandalicus</i> (Rossi, 1790)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus Agnocoris Reuter, 1875							
<i>Agnocoris rubicundus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	+		+	+	+		+
Genus Alloeonotus Fieber, 1858							
<i>Alloeonotus fulvipes</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	+			+			+
Genus Alloeotomus Fieber, 1858							
<i>Alloeotomus gothicus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	+	+	+			+	+
Genus Amblytylus Fieber, 1858							
<i>Amblytylus nasutus</i> (Kirschbaum, 1856)	+			+	+	+	+

Genus Anapus Stål, 1858							
<i>Anapus dorsalis</i> (Reuter, 1890)	+	+	+	+	+	+	
Genus Aphanosoma A. Costa, 1842							
<i>Aphanosoma italicum</i> A. Costa, 1842	+			+			+
Genus Apolygus China, 1941							
<i>Apolygus lucorum</i> (Meyer Dur, 1843)	+			+			
Genus Atomoscelis Reute,r 1875							
<i>Atomoscelis onustus</i> (Fieber, 1861)	+	+	+	+	+		+
Genus Blepharidopterus Kolenati, 1845							
<i>Blepharidopterus angulatus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	+		+	+			
Genus Brachycoleus Fieber, 1858							
<i>Brachycoleus decolor</i> Reuter, 1887	+	+		+	+		+
<i>Brachycoleus lineellus</i> Jakovlev, 1884	+	+		+	+	+	+
Genus Brachynotocoris Reuter, 1880							
<i>Brachynotocoris puncticornis</i> Reuter, 1880	+	+		+	+		
Genus Calocoris Fieber, 1858							
<i>Calocoris angularis</i> Fieber ,1864	+		+	+	+	+	+
<i>Calocoris nebulosus</i> Fieber, 1864	+				+	+	+
<i>Calocoris nemoralis</i> (Fabricius, 1787)					+		
<i>Calocoris roseomaculatus</i> (De Geer, 1773)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus Camponotidea Reuter, 1879							
<i>Camponotidea fieberi</i> Reuter, 1879					+		
Genus Campylomma Reuter, 1878							
<i>Campylomma diversicornis</i> Reuter, 1878	+	+			+	+	+
<i>Campylomma nicolasi</i> Puton & Reuter, 1883	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Campylomma verbasci</i> (Meyer-Dür, 1843)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus Capsus Fabricius, 1803							
<i>Capsus ater</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+		+				+
Genus Charagochilus Fieber, 1858							
<i>Charagochilus gyllenhalii</i> (Fallén, 1807)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus Chlamydatus Curtis, 1833							
<i>Chlamydatus pullus</i> (Reuter, 1870)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus Chlorillus Kerzhner, 1962							
<i>Chlorillus pictus</i> (Fieber, 1864)	+						
Genus Closterotomus Fieber, 1858							

<i>Closterotomus costae</i> (Reuter ,1888)					+		
<i>Closterotomus histrio</i> Reuter, 1877	+			+	+	+	
<i>Closterotomus kroesus</i> (Seidenstücker, 1977)			+		+		
<i>Closterotomus norvegicus</i> (Gmelin, 1790)	+		+	+	+	+	+
Genus Conostethus Fieber, 1858							
<i>Conostethus roseus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	+			+	+	+	
Genus Creontiades Distant, 1883							
<i>Creontiades pallidus</i> (Rambur, 1839)	+	+			+	+	
Genus Criocoris Fieber, 1858							
<i>Criocoris crassicornis</i> (Hahn, 1834)	+						
Genus Deraeocoris Kirschbaum, 1856							
<i>Deraeocoris (Camptobrochis) pallens</i> (Reuter, 1904)	+	+			+	+	
<i>Deraeocoris (Camptobrochis) punctulatus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Deraeocoris (Camptobrochis) serenus</i> (Douglas & Scott, 1868)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Deraeocoris (Deraeocoris) ruber</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+		+	+	+	+	+
<i>Deraeocoris (Deraeocoris) rutilus</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1838)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Deraeocoris (Deraeocoris) ventralis</i> Reuter, 1904	+				+	+	+
<i>Deraeocoris (Knightocapsus) lutescens</i> (Schilling, 1837)	+		+	+		+	+
Genus Dionconotus Reuter, 1894							
<i>Dionconotus neglectus f. major</i> Wagner, 1968					+		
Genus Ehippiocoris Poppius, 1912							
<i>Ehippiocoris lunatus</i> Poppius, 1912	+						
Genus Europiella Reuter, 1909							
<i>Europiella alpina</i> (Reuter, 1875)	+			+			
Genus Eurycolpus Reuter, 1875							
* <i>Eurycolpus aureolus</i> Seidenstücker, 1961	+	+		+	+		
Genus Euryopicoris Reuter, 1875							
<i>Euryopicoris nitidus</i> (Meyer-Dur, 1843)	+				+	+	
Genus Globiceps Lepeletier & Serville, 1825							
<i>Globiceps fulvicollis</i> Jakovlev, 1877	+						+
Genus Grypocoris Douglas & Scott, 1868							
<i>Grypocoris fieberi</i> Douglas & Scott, 1868	+	+	+	+	+		

Genus <i>Halticus</i> Hahn, 1833							
<i>Halticus apterus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+		+	+	+	+	
<i>Halticus luteicollis</i> (Panzer, 1804)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus <i>Heterocordylus</i> Fieber, 1858							
<i>Heterocordylus tumidicornis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1835)	+		+			+	+
Genus <i>Hoplomachus</i> Fieber, 1858							
<i>Hoplomachus thunbergii</i> (Fallen, 1807)	+						
Genus <i>Horistus</i> Fieber, 1860							
<i>Horistus (Horistus) infuscatus</i> (Brullé, 1832)	+						
<i>Horistus orientalis</i> (Gmelin, 1790)	+	+					
<i>Horistus turcomanus</i> (Horvath, 1889)	+				+		
Genus <i>Leptopterna</i> Fieber, 1858							
<i>Leptopterna ferrugata</i> (Fallén, 1807)	+			+			+
Genus <i>Liocoris</i> Fieber, 1858							
<i>Liocoris tripustulatus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus <i>Lygus</i> Hahn, 1833							
<i>Lygus gemellatus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)	+	+		+	+		+
<i>Lygus pratensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Lygus rugulipennis</i> Poppius, 1911	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus <i>Macrolophus</i> Fieber, 1858							
<i>Macrolophus costalis</i> Fieber, 1858	+		+	+	+	+	+
<i>Macrolophus melanotoma</i> (A. Costa, 1853)	+	+		+			
Genus <i>Macrotylus</i> Fieber, 1858							
<i>Macrotylus herrichi</i> (Reuter, 1873)	+	+		+	+		
Genus <i>Malacocoris</i> Fieber, 1858							
<i>Malacocoris chlorizans</i> (Panzer, 1794)	+		+	+	+		+
Genus <i>Megacoelum</i> Fieber, 1858							
<i>Megacoelum</i> sp. cf. <i>brevirostre</i> Reuter, 1879	+						
Genus <i>Megaloceroea</i> Fieber, 1858							
<i>Megaloceroea recticornis</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	+			+	+	+	+
Genus <i>Megalocoleus</i> Reuter, 1890							
<i>Megalocoleus molliculus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	+	+		+	+	+	
Genus <i>Monosynamma</i> J. Scott, 1864							
<i>Monosynamma bohemanii</i> (Fallén, 1829)	+	+		+			+

Genus <i>Nanopsallus</i> Wagner, 1952							
<i>Nanopsallus carduellus</i> (Horvath, 1888)	+	+		+	+	+	+
Genus <i>Notostira</i> Fieber, 1858							
<i>Notostira elongata</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	+		+	+			+
<i>Notostira erratica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Notostira poppiusi</i> Reuter, 1911	+						
Genus <i>Oncotylus</i> Fieber, 1858							
<i>Oncotylus (Cylindromelus) setulosus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1837)	+	+		+	+		+
<i>Oncotylus (Oncotylus) punctipes</i> Reuter, 1875	+					+	
<i>Oncotylus (Oncotylus) pyrethri</i> (Becker, 1864)	+			+	+		
<i>Oncotylus (Oncotylus) viridiflavus</i> (Goeze, 1778)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus <i>Opisthotaenia</i> Reuter, 1901							
<i>Opisthotaenia fulvipes</i> Reuter, 1901	+	+	+	+		+	+
Genus <i>Orthocephalus</i> Fieber, 1858							
<i>Orthocephalus saltator</i> (Hahn, 1835)	+	+			+	+	+
<i>Orthocephalus vittipennis</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)	+	+			+		+
Genus <i>Orthops</i> Fieber, 1858							
<i>Orthops (Montanorthops) campestris</i> (Linnaeus 1758)	+		+	+	+	+	+
<i>Orthops (Montanorthops) forelii</i> Fieber, 1858	+			+			
<i>Orthops (Montanorthops) montanus</i> (Schilling, 1838)	+				+	+	
<i>Orthops (Orthops) basalis</i> (A. Costa, 1853)	+		+	+			
<i>Orthops (Orthops) kalmii</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus <i>Orthotylus</i> Fieber, 1858							
<i>Orthotylus (Melanotrichus) flavosparsus</i> (C.R. Sahlberg, 1841)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Orthotylus (Orthotylus) marginalis</i> Reuter, 1883	+		+	+	+	+	+
<i>Orthotylus (Orthotylus) nassatus</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Orthotylus (Orthotylus) obscurus</i> Reuter, 1875	+						
Genus <i>Paredrocoris</i> Reuter, 1878							
<i>Paredrocoris pectoralis</i> Reuter, 1878	+						
Genus <i>Phoenicocoris</i> Reuter, 1875							
<i>Phoenicocoris obscurellus</i> (Fallén, 1829)	+						
Genus <i>Phytocoris</i> Fallen, 1814							
* <i>Phytocoris (Eckerleinius) obliquoides</i> Wagner, 1959	+			+			

<i>Phytocoris (Exophytocoris) scitulus</i> Reuter, 1908					+		
<i>Phytocoris (Leptophytocoris) cf. chardoni</i> Puton, 1887	+						
<i>Phytocoris (Leptophytocoris) ustulatus</i> Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835	+		+				
<i>Phytocoris (Phytocoris) tiliae</i> (Fabricius, 1777)	+	+	+	+			
Genus Pilophorus Hahn, 1826							
<i>Pilophorus cinnamopterus</i> (Kirschbaum, 1856)	+		+		+	+	+
<i>Pilophorus clavatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)			+	+	+	+	+
<i>Pilophorus pusillus</i> Reuter, 1878	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus Plagiognathus Fieber, 1858							
<i>Plagiognathus bipunctatus</i> Reuter, 1883	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Plagiognathus chrysanthemi</i> (Wolff, 1804)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Plagiognathus fulvipennis</i> (Kirschbaum, 1856)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus Polymerus Hahn, 1831							
<i>Polymerus (Poeciloscytus) cognatus</i> (Fieber, 1858)	+	+	+	+	+		+
<i>Polymerus (Poeciloscytus) microphthalmus</i> Wagner, 1951	+				+	+	
<i>Polymerus (Poeciloscytus) unifasciatus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	+			+	+	+	+
<i>Polymerus (Poeciloscytus) vulneratus</i> (Panzer, 1806)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus Psallus Fieber, 1858							
<i>Psallus lepidus</i> Fieber, 1858	+	+	+				+
* <i>Psallus oleae</i> Wagner, 1963			+		+		
<i>Psallus pinicola</i> Reuter, 1875	+		+	+			
<i>Psallus variabilis</i> Fallen, 1807					+		+
Genus Reuteria Puton, 1875							
<i>Reuteria marqueti</i> Puton, 1875	+				+		+
Genus Rhabdomiris Wagner, 1968							
<i>Rhabdomiris striatellus striatellus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	+						
Genus Stenodema Laporte, 1833							
<i>Stenodema (Brachystira) calcarata</i> (Fallén, 1807)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Stenodema (Brachystira) trispinosa</i> Reuter, 1904	+			+	+		
<i>Stenodema (Stenodema) holsata</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	+		+				+
<i>Stenodema (Stenodema) laevigata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Stenodema (Stenodema) turanica</i> Reuter, 1904	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Stenodema (Stenodema) virens</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Genus <i>Stenotus</i> Jakovlev, 1877							
<i>Stenotus binotatus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	+		+		+		+
Genus <i>Sthenarus</i> Fieber, 1858							
<i>Sthenarus roseri</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus <i>Strongylocoris</i> Blanchard, 1840							
<i>Strongylocoris leucocephalus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+					+	+
<i>Strongylocoris niger</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)	+						+
Genus <i>Taylorilygus</i> Leston, 1952							
<i>Taylorilygus apicalis</i> (Fieber, 1861)							+
Genus <i>Trigonotylus</i> Fieber, 1858							
<i>Trigonotylus pulchellus</i> (Hahn, 1834)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Trigonotylus ruficornis</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Trigonotylus tenuis</i> Reuter, 1893	+						
Family Nabidae A. Costa, 1853							
Genus <i>Himacerus</i> J.P. Wolff, 1811							
<i>Himacerus (Anaptus) major</i> (A. Costa, 1842)	+						
<i>Himacerus (Aptus) mimicooides</i> (O. Costa, 1834)	+		+				
Genus <i>Nabis</i> Latreille, 1802							
<i>Nabis (Nabis) ferus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+				+		
<i>Nabis (Nabis) pseudoferus</i> Remane, 1949	+	+	+	+			+
<i>Nabis (Nabis) pseudoferus orientarius</i> Remane, 1963	+						
<i>Nabis (Nabis) punctatus</i> A. Costa, 1847	+						
Family Reduviidae Latreille, 1807							
Genus <i>Coranus</i> Curtis, 1833							
<i>Coranus griseus</i> (Rossi, 1790)	+	+		+	+	+	
<i>Coranus kerzhneri</i> Putshkov, 1982	+		+			+	+
Genus <i>Ectomocoris</i> Mayr, 1865							
<i>Ectomocoris caucasicus</i> Linnavuori, 1972		+					
<i>Ectomocoris ululans</i> (Rossi, 1970)	+				+		
Genus <i>Nagusta</i> Stål, 1859							
<i>Nagusta goedelii</i> (Kolenati, 1857)	+		+			+	+
Genus <i>Oncocephalus</i> Klug, 1830							
<i>Oncocephalus pilicornis</i> Reuter, 1882					+		
<i>Oncocephalus squalidus</i> (Rossi, 1790)	+				+		

<i>Oncocephalus thoracicus</i> Fieber, 1861			+	+			
Genus Peirates Serville, 1831							
<i>Peirates hybridus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	+	+	+	+	+		
<i>Peirates strepitans</i> Rambur, 1839					+	+	
Genus Reduvius Fabricius, 1775							
<i>Reduvius pallipes</i> Klug, 1830	+	+		+	+	+	+
<i>Reduvius personatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)				+	+	+	+
Genus Rhynocoris Hahn, 1833							
<i>Rhynocoris bipustulatus</i> (Fieber, 1861)					+		
<i>Rhynocoris ibericus</i> Kolenati, 1856	+			+			
<i>Rhynocoris iracundus</i> (Poda, 1761)	+						
<i>Rhynocoris punciventris</i> (Herrich Schaeffer, 1848)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Family Tingidae Laporte, 1832							
Genus Agramma Stephens, 1829							
<i>Agramma (Agramma) laetum</i> (Fallén, 1807)	+						
Genus Catoplatus Spinola, 1837							
<i>Catoplatus brevicornis</i> Akramovskaja & Golub, 1973	+						
<i>Catoplatus carthusianus</i> (Goeze, 1778)	+		+				
<i>Catoplatus hilaris</i> Horváth, 1906	+						
<i>Catoplatus nigriceps</i> Horváth, 1905	+						
Genus Copium Thunberg, 1822							
<i>Copium adumbratum</i> (Horváth, 1891)	+						
<i>Copium clavicorne</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+						
Genus Derephysia Spinola, 1837							
<i>Derephysia (Derephysia) sinuatocollis</i> Puton, 1879	+						
Genus Dictyla Stål, 1874							
<i>Dictyla echii</i> (Schrank, 1782)	+			+			
<i>Dictyla nassata</i> (Puton, 1874)	+						
<i>Dictyla platyoma</i> (Fieber, 1861)	+						
<i>Dictyla rotundata</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)	+						
Genus Elasmotropis Stål, 1874							
<i>Elasmotropis testacea selecta</i> (Horváth, 1891)	+						
Genus Kalama Puton, 1876							
<i>Kalama tricornis</i> (Schrank, 1801)	+						

Genus <i>Monosteira</i> A. Costa, 1862							
<i>Monosteira unicastata</i> (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)	+						
Genus <i>Physatocheila</i> Fieber, 1844							
<i>Physatocheila confinis</i> (Horváth, 1905)	+						
<i>Physatocheila dumetorum</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838)	+		+				
Genus <i>Stephanitis</i> Stål, 1873							
<i>Stephanitis (Stephanitis) pyri</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	+		+	+	+		+
Genus <i>Tingis</i> Fabricius, 1803							
<i>Tingis (Tingis) angustata</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838)	+		+				
<i>Tingis (Tingis) auriculata</i> (A. Costa, 1847)	+		+				
Infraorder Pentatomomorpha							
Family Alydidae Amyot & Serville, 1843							
Genus <i>Alydus</i> Fabricius, 1803							
<i>Alydus calcaratus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+		+	+			
Genus <i>Camptopus</i> Amyot & Serville, 1843							
<i>Camptopus bifasciatus</i> Fieber, 1864	+	+					
<i>Camptopus lateralis</i> (Germar, 1817)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Camptopus tragacanthae</i> (Kolenati, 1845)	+	+					
Genus <i>Megalotomus</i> Fieber, 1860							
<i>Megalotomus ornaticeps</i> (Stål, 1858)	+						
Family Berytidae Fieber, 1851							
Genus <i>Berytinus</i> Kirkaldy, 1900							
<i>Berytinus (Lizinus) geniculatus</i> (Horváth, 1885)	+			+			
Family Coreidae Leach, 1815							
Genus <i>Arenocoris</i> Hahn, 1834							
<i>Arenocoris waltlii</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1834)	+		+				
Genus <i>Bathysolen</i> Fieber, 1860							
<i>Bathysolen nubilus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	+				+		
Genus <i>Centrocoris</i> Kolenati, 1845							
<i>Centrocoris spiniger</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	+	+			+		+
<i>Centrocoris variegatus</i> Kolenati, 1845	+		+	+	+	+	+
Genus <i>Ceraleptus</i> A. Costa, 1847							
<i>Ceraleptus gracilicornis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1835)	+						
Genus <i>Coreus</i> Fabricius, 1794							
<i>Coreus marginatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+		+	+	+	+	+

Genus <i>Coriomeris</i> Westwood, 1842							
<i>Coriomeris affinis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1839)	+						
<i>Coriomeris denticulatus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	+						
<i>Coriomeris hirticornis</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	+		+	+	+	+	+
<i>Coriomeris scabricornis</i> (Panzer, 1809)	+			+	+		+
Genus <i>Enoplops</i> Ammot & Serville, 1843							
<i>Enoplops disciger</i> (Kolenati 1845)	+			+			
Genus <i>Gonocerus</i> Berthold, 1827							
<i>Gonocerus acuteangulatus</i> (Goeze, 1778)	+		+		+	+	+
<i>Gonocerus juniperi</i> Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835					+		
<i>Gonocerus patellatus</i> Kiritshenko, 1916	+						
Genus <i>Leptoglossus</i> Guérin-Méneville, 1831							
<i>Leptoglossus occidentalis</i> Heidemann, 1910				+			+
Genus <i>Phyllomorpha</i> Laporte, 1833							
<i>Phyllomorpha lacerata</i> Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835	+						
<i>Phyllomorpha laciniata</i> (Villers, 1789)	+			+			
Genus <i>Spathocera</i> Stein, 1860							
<i>Spathocera lobata</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1840)	+						
Genus <i>Syromastus</i> Berthold, 1827							
<i>Syrometus rhombeus</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	+					+	+
Family Cydnidae Billberg, 1820							
Genus <i>Cydnus</i> Fabricius, 1803							
<i>Cydnus aterrimus</i> (Forster, 1771)	+				+	+	+
Genus <i>Macrocytus</i> Fieber, 1860							
<i>Macrocytus brunneus</i> (Fabricius, 1803)		+		+	+		
Genus <i>Canthophorus</i> Mulsant & Rey, 1866							
<i>Canthophorus dubius</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	+		+		+	+	+
<i>Canthophorus melanopterus</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1835)	+						
<i>Canthophorus maculipes</i> (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)	+		+				
Genus <i>Legnotus</i> Schiødte, 1848							
<i>Legnotus picipes</i> (Fallén, 1807)	+						
Genus <i>Ochetostethus</i> Fieber, 1860							
<i>Ochetostethus opacus</i> (Scholtz, 1847)	+						
Genus <i>Sehirus</i> Amyot & Serville, 1843							

* <i>Sehirus dissimilis</i> Horváth, 1919	+						+
<i>Sehirus luctuosus</i> Mulsant & Rey, 1866	+						
<i>Sehirus morio</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	+						
<i>Sehirus robustus</i> Horváth, 1895	+						
Genus <i>Tritomegas</i> Amyot & Serville, 1843							
<i>Tritomegas bicolor</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+						
<i>Tritomegas sexmaculatus</i> (Rambur, 1839)	+				+		+
Family <i>Cymidae</i> Baerensprung, 1860							
Genus <i>Cymus</i> Hahn, 1832							
<i>Cymus melanocephalus</i> Fieber, 1861	+		+				
Family <i>Geocoridae</i> Baerensprung, 1860							
Genus <i>Geocoris</i> Fallen, 1814							
<i>Geocoris (Geocoris) megacephalus</i> (Rossi, 1790)						+	
<i>Geocoris (Piocoris) erythrocephalus</i> (Lepeletier & Serville, 1825)	+					+	
Family <i>Heterogastridae</i> Stål, 1872							
Genus <i>Heterogaster</i> Schilling, 1829							
<i>Heterogaster artemisiae</i> Schilling, 1829	+						
<i>Heterogaster cathariae</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	+						
<i>Heterogaster urticae</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	+		+				
Genus <i>Platyplax</i> Fieber, 1860							
<i>Platyplax salviae</i> (Schilling, 1829)	+						
Family <i>Lygaeidae</i> Schilling, 1829							
Genus <i>Kleidocerys</i> Stephens, 1829							
<i>Kleidocerys Resedae</i> (Panzer, 1797)	+						+
Genus <i>Lygaeus</i> Fabricius, 1794							
<i>Lygaeus equestris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+		+	+	+	+	+
Genus <i>Melanocoryphus</i> Stål, 1872							
<i>Melanocoryphus albomaculatus</i> (Goeze, 1778)	+			+			
Genus <i>Nysius</i> Dallas, 1852							
<i>Nysius cymoides</i> (Spinola, 1837)	+		+			+	
<i>Nysius graminicola</i> (Kolenati, 1845)	+		+			+	
<i>Nysius helveticus</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1850)	+		+				
<i>Nysius senecionis</i> (Schilling, 1829)	+		+			+	
<i>Nysius thymi</i> (Wolff, 1804)	+		+			+	

Genus Ortholomus Stål, 1872							
<i>Ortholomus punctipennis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1838)	+						
Genus Paranysius Horváth, 1895							
<i>Paranysius fraterculus</i> Horváth, 1895	+						
Genus Spilostethus Stål, 1868							
<i>Spilostethus pandurus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	+	+	+	+	+	+	
<i>Spilostethus saxatilis</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	+	+		+	+		
Genus Tropidothorax Bergroth, 1894							
<i>Tropidothorax leucopterus</i> (Goeze, 1778)	+		+		+	+	
Family Oxycarenidae Stål, 1862							
Genus Auchenodes Horvath, 1891							
<i>Auchenodes costalis</i> (Lethierry, 1877)	+						
Genus Macroplax Fieber, 1860							
<i>Macroplax fasciata</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1835)	+						
Genus Metopoplax Fieber, 1860							
<i>Metopoplax origani</i> (Kolenati, 1845)	+				+		+
Genus Microplax Fieber, 1860							
<i>Microplax interrupta</i> (Fieber, 1837)	+						
Genus Oxycarenum Fieber, 1837							
<i>Oxycarenum (Euoxycarenum) pallens</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1850)	+						
<i>Oxycarenum (Oxycarenum) hyalinipennis</i> (A. Costa, 1843)						+	+
Family Pachygronthidae Stål, 1865							
Genus Cymophyes Fieber, 1870							
<i>Cymophyes ochroleuca</i> Fieber, 1870					+		
Family Pentatomidae Leach, 1815							
Genus Acrosternum Fieber, 1861							
<i>Acrosternum breviceps</i> (Jakovlev, 1889)					+		
<i>Acrosternum heegeri</i> Fieber, 1861	+		+		+	+	+
<i>Acrosternum millieri</i> (Mulsant & Rey, 1866)	+						
Genus Aelia Fabricius, 1803							
<i>Aelia acuminata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+		+	+	+		+
<i>Aelia furcula</i> Fieber, 1868	+	+	+	+	+	+	
<i>Aelia rostrata</i> Boheman, 1852	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Aelia virgata</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1841)	+	+		+			

Genus <i>Ancyrosoma</i> Amyot & Serville, 1843							
<i>Ancyrosoma leucogrammes</i> (Gmelin, 1790)	+		+	+	+	+	+
Genus <i>Antheminia</i> Mulsant & Rey, 1866							
<i>Antheminia lunulata</i> (Goeze, 1778)	+		+	+			
<i>Antheminia pusio</i> (Kolenati, 1846)	+			+			
Genus <i>Apodiphus</i> Spinola, 1837							
<i>Apodiphus amygdali</i> (Germar, 1817)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus <i>Bagrada</i> Stål, 1862							
<i>Bagrada (Nitilia) abellei</i> Puton, 1881	+		+				
<i>Bagrada (Nitilia) kaufmanni</i> Oshanin, 1870	+		+				
Genus <i>Brachynema</i> Mulsant & Rey, 1852							
<i>Brachynema cinctum</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	+						
<i>Brachynema germarii</i> (Kolenati, 1846)					+		
Genus <i>Carpocoris</i> Kolenati, 1846							
<i>Carpocoris (Carpocoris) coreanus</i> Distant, 1899	+						
<i>Carpocoris (Carpocoris) fuscispinus</i> (Boheman, 1849)	+		+	+	+		+
<i>Carpocoris (Carpocoris) mediterraneus</i> Tamanini, 1958	+		+	+	+	+	+
<i>Carpocoris (Carpocoris) melanocerus</i> Mulsant, 1852			+	+	+	+	
<i>Carpocoris (Carpocoris) pudicus</i> (Poda, 1761)	+		+		+	+	+
<i>Carpocoris (Carpocoris) purpureipennis</i> (De Geer, 1773)	+		+	+	+	+	+
Genus <i>Chlorochroa</i> Stål, 1872							
<i>Chlorochroa (Rhytidolomia) juniperina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+						
Genus <i>Cnephosa</i> Jakovlev, 1880							
<i>Cnephosa flavomarginata</i> Jakovlev, 1880	+						
Genus <i>Codophila</i> Mulsant & Rey, 1866							
<i>Codophila maculicollis</i> (Dallas, 1851)	+		+		+	+	+
<i>Codophila pusio</i> (Kolenati, 1846)	+			+			
<i>Codophila varia</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	+			+	+	+	
Genus <i>Derula</i> Mulsant & Rey, 1856							
<i>Derula flavoguttata</i> Mulsant & Rey, 1856	+						
Genus <i>Dolycoris</i> Mulsant & Rey, 1866							
<i>Dolycoris baccarum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Genus Eurydema Laporte De Castelnau, 1832							
<i>Eurydema blandum</i> Horvath, 1903	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Eurydema (Horvatheurydema) fieberi</i> Fieber, 1837	+				+		
* <i>Eurydema formosum</i> (Puton, 1895)		+					
<i>Eurydema laticolle</i> Horvath, 1907					+		
<i>Eurydema (Eurydema) oleraceum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+		+	+	+		+
<i>Eurydema (Eurydema) ornatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Eurydema (Horvatheurydema) rugulosa</i> (Dohrn, 1860)					+		
<i>Eurydema (Rubrodorsalium) ventrale</i> Kolenati, 1846	+		+		+	+	+
Genus Eysarcoris Hahn, 1834							
<i>Eysarcoris inconspicuus</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1844)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Eysarcoris ventralis</i> (Westwood, 1837)	+		+		+	+	+
Genus Graphosoma Laporte De Castelnau, 1832							
<i>Graphosoma italicum</i> (Müller, 1766)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Graphosoma lineatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+		+	+	+	+	+
<i>Graphosoma melanoxanthum</i> Horvath, 1903	+						
<i>Graphosoma semipunctatum</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Graphosoma stali</i> Horváth, 1881		+					
Genus Holcostethus Fieber, 1860							
<i>Holcostethus albipes</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	+						+
<i>Holcostethus vernalis</i> (Wolff, 1804)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus Jalla Hahn, 1832							
<i>Jalla dumosa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)				+			
Genus Mustha Amyot & Serville, 1843							
<i>Mustha spinosula</i> (Lefebvre, 1831)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Mustha vicina</i> Hoberlandt, 1997		+					
Genus Neottiglossa Kirby, 1837							
<i>Neottiglossa bifida</i> (A. Costa, 1847)	+			+			+
<i>Neottiglossa leporina</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1830)	+		+	+	+	+	
Genus Nezara Amyot & Serville, 1843							
<i>Nezara viridula</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus Palomena Mulsant & Rey, 1860							
<i>Palomena prasina</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	+		+	+	+	+	+
Genus Pausias Jakovlev, 1905							

<i>Pausias martini</i> (Puton, 1890)					+		
Genus <i>Picromerus</i> Amyot & Serville, 1843							
* <i>Picromerus brachypterus</i> Ahmad & Önder, 1990			+			+	
Genus <i>Piezodorus</i> Fieber, 1860							
<i>Piezodorus lituratus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	+	+	+		+		
Genus <i>Podops</i> Laporte, 1833							
<i>Podops (Opocrates) rectidens</i> Horvath, 1883							+
Genus <i>Putonia</i> Stål, 1872							
<i>Putonia asiatica</i> Jakovlev, 1885	+						
Genus <i>Rhaphigaster</i> Laporte De Castelnau, 1862							
<i>Rhaphigaster nebulosa</i> (Pod,a 1761)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus <i>Rhombocoris</i> Mary, 1864							
<i>Rhombocoris regularis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)	+						
Genus <i>Risibia</i> Horváth, 1888							
<i>Risibia verbasci</i> Lodos & Önder, 1980	+						
Genus <i>Sciocoris</i> Fallén, 1829							
<i>Sciocoris (Sciocoris) amoenus</i> (Brullé, 1832)	+		+	+			
<i>Sciocoris (Sciocoris) cursitans</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	+						
<i>Sciocoris (Sciocoris) distinctus</i> Fieber, 1851	+			+			
<i>Sciocoris (Sciocoris) macrocephalus</i> Fieber, 1851	+						
<i>Sciocoris (Sciocoris) ochraceus</i> Fieber, 1861					+		
<i>Sciocoris (Sciocoris) ogivus</i> Jakovlev, 1894	+						
<i>Sciocoris (Sciocoris) sulcatus</i> Fieber, 1851	+						
Genus <i>Stagonomus</i> Gorski, 1852							
<i>Stagonomus (Stagonomus) amoenus</i> (Brullé, 1832)	+		+	+			
<i>Stagonomus (Stagonomus) bipunctatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+		+		+		+
<i>Stagonomus (Stagonomus) pusillus</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1830)					+		
Genus <i>Staria</i> Dohrn, 1860							
<i>Staria lunata</i> (Hahn, 1835)	+						+
Genus <i>Stenozygum</i> Fieber, 1861							
<i>Stenozygum coloratum</i> (Klug, 1845)					+		
Genus <i>Tarisa</i> Amyot & Serville, 1843							
<i>Tarisa virescens</i> Herrich-Schäffer, 1851	+						
Genus <i>Tholagmus</i> Stål, 1860							

<i>Tholagmus flavolineatus</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	+				+		
Genus <i>Ventocoris</i> Hahn, 1834							
<i>Ventocoris (Selenodera) achivus</i> (Horváth, 1889)					+		
<i>Ventocoris (Selenodera) fischeri</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)					+	+	
<i>Ventocoris (Selenodera) halophilus</i> (Jakovlev, 1874)	+						
<i>Ventocoris (Ventocoris) rusticus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)				+	+	+	
Genus <i>Zicrona</i> Amyot & Serville, 1843							
<i>Zicrona coerulea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+		+		+		
Family Piesmatidae Amyot & Serville, 1843							
Genus <i>Piesma</i> Lepeletier & Serville, 1828							
<i>Piesma maculatum</i> (Laporte, 1833)	+						
Genus <i>Parapiesma</i> Péricart, 1974							
<i>Parapiesma atriplicis</i> (Frey-Gessner, 1863)	+						
<i>Parapiesma salsolae</i> (Becker, 1867)	+						
Family Plataspidae Dallas, 1851							
Genus <i>Coptosoma</i> Laporte, 1833							
<i>Coptosoma scutellatum</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	+						
Family Pyrrhocoridae Fieber, 1860							
Genus <i>Pyrrhocoris</i> Fallen, 1814							
<i>Pyrrhocoris apterus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Pyrrhocoris marginatus</i> (Kolenati, 1845)	+						
Genus <i>Scantius</i> Stål, 1866							
<i>Scantius aegyptius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+	+		+	+		
Family Rhopalidae Amyot & Audinet-Serville, 1843							
Genus <i>Agraphopus</i> Stal, 1872							
<i>Agraphopus lethierryi</i> Stal, 1872	+						
Genus <i>Brachycarenum</i> Fieber, 1861							
<i>Brachycarenum tigrinus</i> (Schilling, 1829)	+	+	+	+	+		+
Genus <i>Chorosoma</i> Curtis, 1830							
<i>Chorosoma schillingii</i> (Schilling, 1829)	+				+		
Genus <i>Corizomorpha</i> Jakovlev, 1883							
<i>Corizomorpha janowskyi</i> Jakovlev, 1883	+						
Genus <i>Corizus</i> Fallén, 1814							
<i>Corizus hyoscyami</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Genus <i>Liorhyssus</i> Stål, 1872							
<i>Liorhyssus hyalinus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Genus <i>Maccevethus</i> Dallas, 1852							
<i>Maccevethus caucasicus</i> (Kolenati, 1845)	+	+	+	+			
<i>Maccevethus corsicus</i> Signoret, 1862	+						+
<i>Maccevethus errans</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	+						
Genus <i>Rhopalus</i> Schilling, 1827							
<i>Rhopalus (Aeschyntelus) maculatus</i> (Fieber, 1837)	+						
<i>Rhopalus (Rhopalus) conspersus</i> (Fieber, 1837)	+						
<i>Rhopalus (Rhopalus) parumpunctatus</i> Schilling, 1829	+						
<i>Rhopalus (Rhopalus) rufus</i> Schilling, 1829	+			+	+		+
<i>Rhopalus (Rhopalus) subrufus</i> (Gmelin, 1790)	+	+					+
Genus <i>Stictopleurus</i> Stål, 1872							
<i>Stictopleurus abutilon</i> (Rossi, 1790)	+						
<i>Stictopleurus pictus</i> (Fieber, 1861)	+	+					
<i>Stictopleurus punctatonervosus</i> (Goeze, 1778)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Stictopleurus subtomentosus</i> (Rey, 1888)	+						
<i>Stictopleurus unicolor</i> (Jakovlev, 1873)	+						
Family Rhyparochromidae Amyot & Audinet-Serville, 1843							
Genus <i>Aellopus</i> Wolff, 1811							
<i>Aellopus atratus</i> (Goeze, 1778)				+			
Genus <i>Aphanus</i> Laporte de Castelnau, 1833							
<i>Aphanus rolandri</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+						
Genus <i>Beosus</i> Amyot & Serville, 1843							
<i>Beosus maritimus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	+	+	+	+	+	+	
<i>Beosus quadripunctatus</i> (Müller, 1766)	+		+				
Genus <i>Drymus</i> Fieber, 1860							
<i>Drymus (Sylvadrymus) brunneus confinis</i> Reuter, 1893	+						
<i>Drymus (Sylvadrymus) sylvaticus</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	+						
Genus <i>Emblethis</i> Fieber, 1860							
<i>Emblethis denticollis</i> Horváth, 1878	+		+	+	+		
<i>Emblethis osmanus</i> Seidenstücker, 1963	+		+	+	+	+	
Genus <i>Gastrodes</i> Westwood, 1840							

<i>Gastrodes grossipes</i> (De Geer, 1773)	+						
Genus Graptopeltus Stål, 1872							
<i>Graptopeltus lynceus</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	+						
Genus Lasiocoris Fieber, 1860							
<i>Lasiocoris anomalus</i> (Kolenati, 1845)	+						
Genus Megalonotus Fieber, 1860							
<i>Megalonotus sabulicola</i> (Thomson, 1870)	+						
Genus Paromius Fieber, 1860							
<i>Paromius gracilis</i> (Rambur, 1839)	+						
Genus Peritrechus Fieber, 1860							
<i>Peritrechus geniculatus</i> (Hahn, 1832)	+						
<i>Peritrechus gracilicornis</i> Puton, 1877	+		+				
Genus Plinthisus Stephen, 1829							
<i>Plinthisus (Plinthisus) major</i> Horváth, 1876	+						
Genus Pterotmetus Amyot & Serville, 1843							
<i>Pterotmetus staphyliniformis</i> (Schilling, 1829)	+			+			
Genus Raglius Stål, 1872							
<i>Raglius confusus</i> (Reuter, 1886)	+						+
Genus Rhyparochromus Hahn, 1826							
<i>Rhyparochromus pini</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+			+	+		
<i>Rhyparochromus phoeniceus</i> (Rossi, 1794)	+						
<i>Rhyparochromus sanguineus</i> (Douglas & Scott, 1868)	+						
<i>Rhyparochromus vulgaris</i> (Schilling, 1829)	+				+		
Genus Remaudiereana Hoberlandt, 1954							
<i>Remaudiereana annulipes</i> (Baerensprung, 1859)					+		
Genus Scolopostethus Fieber, 1860							
<i>Scolopostethus affinis</i> (Schilling, 1829)	+						
Genus Stygnocoris Douglas & Scott, 1865							
<i>Stygnocoris rusticus</i> (Fallen, 1807)	+						
Genus Xanthochilus Stål, 1872							
<i>Xanthochilus quadratus</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	+				+		
<i>Xanthochilus saturnius</i> (Rossi, 1790)	+						
Family Scutelleridae Leach, 1815							
Genus Solenosthedium Spinola, 1837							

<i>Solenosthedium bilunatum</i> (Lefebvre, 1827)					+		
Genus Eurygaster Laporte, 1833							
<i>Eurygaster austriaca</i> (Schrank, 1776)	+		+	+	+		+
<i>Eurygaster dilaticollis</i> Dohrn, 1860	+		+	+			
<i>Eurygaster integriceps</i> Puton, 1881	+	+	+	+	+		+
<i>Eurygaster maura</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+	+	+	+	+		
<i>Eurygaster testudinaria</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	+						
Genus Psacasta Germar, 1839							
<i>Psacasta (Psacasta) exanthematica</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	+			+			
Genus Odontoscelis Laporte, 1833							
<i>Odontoscelis (Odontoscelis) fuliginosa</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	+						
Genus Ellipsocoris Mayr, 1864							
<i>Ellipsocoris trilineatus</i> Mayr, 1864	+						
Genus Odontotarsus Laporte, 1833							
<i>Odontotarsus impictus</i> Jakovlev, 1886	+	+					
<i>Odontotarsus purpureolineatus</i> (Rossi, 1790)	+		+	+	+		+
<i>Odontotarsus rufescens</i> Fieber, 1861	+	+	+	+	+		+
Genus Phimodera Germar, 1839							
<i>Phimodera flori</i> Fieber, 1863	+						
Family Stenocephalidae Dallas, 1852							
Genus Dicranocephalus Hahn, 1826							
<i>Dicranocephalus agilis</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	+		+	+	+	+	+
<i>Dicranocephalus albipes</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	+		+			+	
<i>Dicranocephalus setulosus</i> (Ferrari, 1874)	+						
Subtotal	357	105	156	171	201	121	146

Remarks: **EA** - Eastern Anatolia, **SA** - Southeastern Anatolia, **BS** - Black Sea, **CA** - Central Anatolia, **MD** - Mediterranean, **A** - Aegean, **M** - Marmara.

There are great differences in species composition and richness between the geographic regions of Türkiye (Tab. 1, Fig. 2). In this study, 357 species, 205 families of the Heteroptera have been recorded from Eastern Anatolia (87,7% of the recorded species), 105 species, 71 genera and 14 families from South-eastern Anatolia (25,8%), 156 species, 98 genera and 17 families from Black Sea (38,3%), 171 species, 112 genera and 20 families from Central

Figure 2. Number of species, genera, and families of Heteroptera in the biogeographical regions of Türkiye (EA - Eastern Anatolia, SA - Southeastern Anatolia, BS - Black Sea, CA - Central Anatolia, MD -Mediterranean, A - Aegean, M - Marmara).

Table 2: Distribution of endemic species in Biogeographic Regions of Türkiye

	EA	SA	BS	CA	MD	A	M
<i>Eurycolpus aureolus</i> Seidenstücker, 1961	+	+		+	+		
<i>Phytocoris (Eckerleinius) obliquoides</i> Wagner, 1959	+			+			
<i>Psallus oleae</i> Wagner, 1963			+		+		
<i>Picromerus brachypterus</i> Ahmad & Önder, 1990			+			+	
Total species	2	1	2	2	2	1	

There are great differences in endemic species composition and richness between the bio-geographic regions of Türkiye (Tab. 2). In this study have been recorded two species from Eastern Anatolia, one species from Southeastern Anatolia, two species from Black Sea, two species from Central Anatolia, two species from Mediterranean, one species Aegean and one species from Marmara. As a result, there is a high probability that all geographical regions can also appear.

DISCUSSION

Infraorder Gerromorpha are surface inhabiting taxa found in a wide array of habitats from the smallest, often temporary, bodies of fresh water to the world's open oceans. They in eight families are represented by more than 2000 species and 150 genera (J. Polhemus & D. Polhemus, 2008; Henry, 2017). In the Palearctic region, they are represented by 248 species from 42 genera (Aukema et al., 2013),

while they are represented by 38 species and subspecies from 9 genera within 5 families in our country (Yazıcı 2020; Fent et al., 2011). This study also reported 4 species belonging to 2 genera and one family from Gerromorpha (Gerridae family).

The Nepomorpha are characterized by short antennae concealed partly or entirely by the eyes. All are predatory, except some Corixidae. Most can inflict painful bites. Almost all of them are aquatic and have legs modified for swimming (Schuh & Slater, 1995; Henry, 2017). Approximately 140 genera and 2309 species of Nepomorpha are known (Polhemus & Polhemus, 2008). This number in the Palearctic region is 268 species of 41 genera (Henry, 2017) while they are represented by 55 species and subspecies from 19 genera within 9 families in Türkiye (Yazıcı, 2020, Fent et al., 2011). This study reported 10 species belonging to 5 genera and 4 families from Nepomorpha (Belostomatidae, Corixidae, Nepidae and Notonectidae families).

Infraorder Leptopodomorpha comprises four families separated into the superfamilies Leptopodoidea and Saldoidea (Henry, 2017). There are known 381 species and 64 genera in the World (Henry, 2017). This number is 268 species and 41 genera in the Palearctic region while 21 species belong to 7 genera and two families in Türkiye (Yazıcı & Bal, 2022). This study reported 3 species belonging to one genus and one family from Leptopodomorpha.

The Cimicomorpha is one of the largest and highly diversified infraorder of the Heteroptera. All members' rostrum and other morphology are adapted to feeding on animals as their prey or hosts (Kuznetsova et al., 2011). The Cimicomorpha has been separated into seven superfamilies and 17 families, including the two largest Heteropteran families, the Miridae and Reduviidae (Henry, 2017). All World known 21.271 species and 2945 genera of Cimicomorpha. In Palearctic Region recorded 5223 species belonging to 718 genera and 13 families (Aukema et

al., 2013). This number is 838 species and 9 families in Türkiye (Tezcan, 2024). This study reported 177 species belonging to 93 genera and 6 families from Cimicomorpha.

Six superfamilies have been recognized in a phylogenetic analysis of the Pentatomomorpha. The monophyly of the Pentatomomorpha is supported by at least six synapomorphies that include the presence of lamellate pulvilli, abdominal trichobothria, an apically bulbous spermatheca, similar accessory salivary glands, an embryonic egg burster, and lack of a true operculum (Henry, 2017). They have been 18.411 species belonging to 2750 genera in the World (Henry, 2017). This number is 3502 species and 782 genera in the Palearctic region (Aukema et al., 2013) while there are more than 665 species and 18 families in Türkiye (Tezcan, 2024). This study reported 213 species belonging to 120 genera and 18 families from Pentatomomorpha.

In this study, total 407 species of 221 genera belonging to 30 families of Heteroptera were recorded from Atatürk University Biodiversity Science Museum (ABBM) Erzurum in Türkiye: 5 species belonging to 3 genera of Alydidae, 8 species belonging to 4 genera of Anthocoridae, 1 species belonging to 1 genus of Belostomatidae, 1 species belonging to 1 genus of Berytidae, 19 species belonging to 12 genera of Coreidae, 5 species belonging to 2 genera of Corixidae, 13 species belonging to 7 genera of Cydnidae, 1 species belonging to 1 genus of Cymidae, 2 species belonging to 1 genus of Geocoridae, 4 species belonging to 2 genera of Gerridae, 4 species belonging to 2 genera of Heterogastridae, 1 species belonging to 1 genus of Lyctoridae, 13 species belonging to 8 genera of Lygaeidae, 126 species belonging to 68 genera of Miridae, 6 species belonging to 2 genera of Nabidae, 1 species belonging to 1 genus of Nepidae, 3 species belonging to 1 genus of Notonectidae, 6 species belonging to 5 genera of Oxycarenidae, 1

species belonging to 1 genus of *Sthenarus roseri* (Herrich-Schaeffer), Pachygronthidae, 79 species belonging to 38 genera of Pentatomidae, 3 species belonging to 2 genera of Piesmatidae, 1 species belonging to 1 genus of Plataspidae, 3 species belonging to 2 genera of Pyrrhocoridae, 16 species belonging to 7 genera of Reduviidae, 19 species belonging to 9 genera of Rhopalidae, 27 species belonging to 19 genera of Rhyparochromidae, 3 species belonging to 1 genus of Saldidae, 13 species belonging to 7 genera of Scutelleridae, 3 species belonging to 1 genus of Stenocephalidae, 20 species belonging to 11 genera of Tingidae, Among them, four species are endemic. They are *Eurycolpus aureolus* Seidenstücker 1961, *Phytocoris (Eckerleinius) obliquoides* Wagner 1959, *Psallus oleae* Wagner 1963, and *Picromerus brachypterus* Ahmad & Önder 1990 are considered to be endemic (Table 1,2).

Additionally, the most widespread species in all zoogeographic regions are (Table 1): *Camptopus lateralis* (Germar) (Alydidae), *Orius (O.) niger* (Wolff) (Anthocoridae), *Adelphocoris lineolatus* (Goeze), *Adelphocoris vandalicus* (Rossi), *Calocoris roseomaculatus* (De Geer), *Campylomma nicolasi* Puton and Reuter, *Campylomma verbasci* (Meyer-Dür), *Charagochilus gyllenhalii* (Fallén), *Chlamydatus pullus* (Reuter), *Deraeocoris (Camptobrochis) punctulatus* (Fallén), *Deraeocoris (Camptobrochis) serenus* (Douglas & Scott), *Deraeocoris (Deraeocoris) rutilus* (Herrich-Schäffer), *Halticus luteicollis* (Panzer), *Liocoris tripustulatus* (Fabricius), *Lygus pratensis* (Linnaeus), *Lygus rugulipennis* Poppius, *Notostira erratica* (Linnaeus), *Oncotylus (O.) viridiflavus* (Goeze), *Orthops (Orthops) kalmii* (Linnaeus), *Orthotylus (Melanotrichus) flavosparsus* (C.R. Sahlberg), *Orthotylus (O.) nassatus* (Fabricius), *Pilophorus pusillus* Reuter, *Plagiognathus bipunctatus* Reuter, *Plagiognathus chrysanthemi* (Wolff), *Plagiognathus fulvipennis* (Kirschbaum), *Polymerus (Poeciloscytus) vulneratus* (Panzer), *Stenodema (Brachystira) calcarata* (Fallén), *Stenodema (S.) laevigata* (Linnaeus), *Stenodema (S.) turanica* Reuter, *Stenodema (S.) virens* (Linnaeus),

In this study, 4 species in 2 genera of Gerromorpha, 10 species in 5 genera of Nepomorpha, 3 species in one genus of Leptopodomorpha, 177 species in 92 genera of Cimicomorpha and 216 species in 121 genera of Pentatomomorpha are recorded. In total, 407 species belonging to 221 genera of 30 families of Heteroptera are recorded from Atatürk University Biodiversity Science Museum (ABBM) Erzurum in Türkiye. This number corresponds to 26% of Türkiye's Heteroptera. The study revealed that there are great differences in species composition and richness between the geographic regions of Türkiye. Especially the diversity of species (357), genus (205) and family (27) is highest in the Eastern Anatolia region. Çerçi et al. (2022) conducted a study of Heteroptera species collected from numerous localities in Anatolia, particularly Eastern Anatolia, between 1998 and 2021, and 124 species in 97 genera belonging to 20 families were recorded.

Turkish Heteroptera fauna is very rich. The great richness and diversity of the Turkish Heteroptera fauna are the result of the various topographic and climatic structure of the country. On the other hand, Türkiye is a boundary of East Mediterranean, Euro-Siberian and Irano-Turanian provinces of the Palaearctic region that caused the richness of the

fauna and it is a country that is located as a bridge between Europe and Asia. It has different climatic conditions. Both geographic position and climatic differentiations have some effects on flora and fauna. Because of this, Türkiye has been focused by Turkish and foreign scientists for a long period. However, the knowledge of Türkiye's Heteroptera fauna is still in-

complete despite the research for more than a century when considering studies in recent years. At this point, we hope that our study will encourage further research on Heteroptera in Türkiye. Such data will create a solid base for zoo-geographic research on the Turkish fauna.

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